

Chemistry of molecular precursors for compound semiconductor nanoparticles[†]

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Abstract : This lecture intends to present recent results on design and development of molecular precursors for the synthesis of some binary and ternary compound semiconductor nanoparticles. A wide variety of complexes of Group II, III, IV and V elements with dithiocarboxylate, xanthate, dithiocarbamate, selenocarboxylate and *N,N*-dimethylaminoalkylchalcogenolates have been prepared and characterized by spectroscopic and single crystal X-ray diffraction techniques. Several of these complexes on thermolysis yield bulk as well as nanoparticles of metal chalcogenides (ME : M = Zn, Cd, Hg, Pb; E = S, Se, Te) and M₂S₃ (M = In, Sb, Bi). The latter have been characterized by XRD, EDAX, SEM, TEM, SAED and photoluminescence.

Keywords : Endowment lecture, molecular precursors, nano particles, metal chalcogenides, photoluminescence.

Introduction

I am thankful to the Indian Chemical Society for selecting me for Professor Priyadarajan Ray Memorial Award for the year 2006. It is indeed a great honor for me and for my group to receive such a prestigious award from one of the oldest scientific societies in the country.

Since time immemorial materials spectrum has always been in a dynamic state. There has been an insatiable quest to develop either new materials or modify the properties of already known material so that new/changed properties can be used in some beneficial ways. One can modify properties of a material at least in three possible ways, viz. (i) by changing purity level, (ii) by modifying phase, and (iii) by altering the size. The change in properties of a matter with size and shape has been recognized only recently with the emergence of a broad field of nano-science and nano-technology. Although use of colloidal metals in dyeing glass and fabrics and as therapeutic agents was known since Roman period, the field has grown exponentially in the last two decades¹. For instance there were only a few publications on silver and gold nanoparticles before 1990, but in 2004 alone more than 5000 papers were published dealing with the nanoparticles of silver and gold². The literature on nano-materials is primarily dominated by papers describing their synthesis. As the materials' properties are size and

shape dependent, there is always a need to generate nanoparticles of desired size, shape and monodispersity. This need has been a driving force to develop newer and refined synthetic routes. Accordingly many synthetic strategies based on physical (top-down or fabrication approach, e.g. ion sputtering, spray pyrolysis, etc.) and chemical (bottom-up or synthetic approach, e.g. solvothermal, electrochemical, etc.) methods have evolved. The bottom-up approach usually employs an agent to stop growth of particles at the nanoscale. Capping materials, such as surfactants or polymer, are used in this approach so as to prevent aggregation and/or precipitation of nanoparticles from the reaction medium.

For unitary materials, like Cu, Ag, Au, Pd, Pt nanoparticles, chemical reduction of their metal salts, which are commercially available, is quite versatile and is used routinely¹. However, for binary, ternary and quaternary materials, stoichiometry requirements pose several synthetic challenges. For the preparation of such materials a user-friendly synthetic approach is desirable at least for those scientists and engineers who are interested in properties and applications but are not experts in synthetic chemistry. An easily adoptable synthetic approach for such materials would be a single source precursor route. Some of the results using this approach are presented here.

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~45 ppm from its position in the free ligand (δ 380 ppm). The coordination environment around cadmium atom in $[\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2\{(\text{SeImMe})_2\}]$ is distorted octahedral and is defined by O_4N_2 core of two asymmetrically chelated acetate groups and the chelating diselenide (Fig. 6)¹⁷. These complexes undergo two-three steps decomposition (from TG) and on thermolysis in HDA-TOPO yield either cubic MSe ($M = \text{Zn}, \text{Hg}$) or hexagonal CdSe nanoparticles with an average diameter of 6–10 nm (from XRD and TEM)¹⁷.

Fig. 6. Molecular structure of $[\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2\{\text{MeImSe}_2\}]$.

(iii) Precursors for mercury telluride :

Unlike zinc and cadmium chalcogenides, synthesis of mercury chalcogenide nanoparticles is rather difficult. The single source precursor strategy has led to little success as the molecules like $\text{Hg}(\text{ER})_2$ on pyrolysis yield mercury metal and R_2E_2 rather than HgE ¹⁸. Our approach to use internally functionalized organochalcogenolate ligands has been quite convenient for the preparation of mercury telluride nanoparticles. Accordingly, the complex $[\text{Hg}(\text{TeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2)_2]$ was prepared by the reaction of $[\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tmeda})]$ with $\text{NaTeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2$ in methanol¹⁹. The mass spectrum of the complex exhibits molecular ion peak and also peak due to HgTe . No peaks attributable to mercury or tellurium ions have been observed. The ^{119}Hg (Fig. 7) and ^{125}Te NMR spectra of this complex showed signals at δ -1800 and -1171 ppm, respectively¹⁹.

Thermolysis of this complex either in a furnace (120–200 °C) or in a coordinating solvent at 90 °C afforded mercury telluride nanoparticles (Fig. 8) with an average diameter of 6 nm. If pyrolysis is carried out in the presence of $\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the particles were doped with manganese. The samples doped with 2.7% manganese showed ferromagnetism at room temperature¹⁹.

Fig. 7. ^{119}Hg NMR spectrum of $[\text{Hg}(\text{TeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2)_2]$

Fig. 8. XRD pattern of HgTe prepared by pyrolysis of $[\text{Hg}(\text{TeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2)_2]$

(2) Precursors for III-VI materials

Group-III metals from a variety of binary chalcogenides differing in composition and structure²⁰. The III-VI materials, particularly those of gallium and indium, find numerous applications in opto-electronics, non-linear optics, photo-voltaic devices and also as passivating agents for III-V films.

Although there are a number of reports on the preparation of III-VI thin films, synthesis of their nanoparticles are evolving. Single source precursor route, developed by us and others, is emerging as a convenient preparative method²¹. A variety of classical and organometallic dithiolate complexes of gallium and indium have been prepared (Scheme 3)^{22–26}.

These complexes are discrete monomers. Several of them have been characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction (Fig. 9). Tris xanthates of indium, $[\text{In}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3]$ and diorganoindium dithiolates have been used as precursors

Scheme 3

sors for indium sulfide nanoparticles. Thermolysis of $\text{In}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ in ethylene glycol and $\text{In}(\text{S}_2\text{CAr})_3$ (Ar = Ph or tol) in HDA afforded yellow-orange cubic $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ nanoparticles of 13–30 nm (from XRD and TEM). The nanoparticles exhibited a blue shifted emission at 440 nm in their PL spectra suggesting their quantum confinement.

Fig. 9. Molecular structure of $[\text{In}(\text{S}_2\text{COPr})_3]$.

(3) Precursors for lead chalcogenide nanoparticles

Lead chalcogenides have been used for many centuries in various cosmetic preparations²⁷. Lately they are used as IR detectors and also as thermoelectric materials^{28,29}. Although several synthetic routes have been used to prepare different geometries of PbE (E = S, Se, Te) nanoparticles^{29,30}, single source precursor strategy has begun to receive attention only recently³¹. The complexes, $[\text{Pb}(\text{S}_2\text{CAr})_2]$ (Ar = Ph or tol), $[\text{Pb}(\text{SeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOMe})_2]$ and $[\text{Pb}(\text{SeCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2)_2]$ have been synthesized by the reactions of lead acetate with appropriate organochalcogen ligands. These complexes on thermolysis in HDA give PbE (E = S or Se) nanoparticles. The latter have been characterized by XRD (Fig. 10) and EDAX³².

(4) Precursors for antimony and bismuth sulfide nanoparticles

The V-VI compounds, due to their photovoltaic properties and high thermoelectric power, are used in opto-

Fig. 10. XRD pattern of PbSe obtained at room temperature by the reaction between lead acetate and PhCOSeK .

electronic and thermo-electronic devices³³. Polymer coated Bi_2S_3 nanoparticles have been used as imaging agent in X-ray computed tomography³⁴.

Dithiolate complexes of group-V have been extensively investigated over the past few decades³⁵ but their role as single source precursors for the synthesis of metal sulfide nanoparticles has been realized only recently^{36,37}. Tris dithiocarboxylates of antimony and bismuth $[\text{M}(\text{S}_2\text{CAr})_3]$ (M = Sb or Bi; Ar = Ph or tol) have been synthesized and characterized. The X-ray structure revealed chelating dithiocarboxylate ligands (Fig. 11)³⁸. Pyrolysis in diphenylether gave M_2S_3 (M = Sb, Bi) nanoparticles as confirmed from their XRD pattern (Fig. 12) and EDAX.

Fig. 11. Molecular structure of $[\text{Sb}(\text{S}_2\text{Ctol})_3]$.

(5) Precursors for CuInSe_2 nanoparticles

The ternary chalcogenide materials have been studied extensively for solar cell applications. The CuInSe_2 is considered the front runner for solar cells. The single source precursors $[\text{CuIn}(\text{SeCOAr})_4(\text{PR}_3)_2]$, have been syn-

Fig.12. XRD pattern of Sb_2S_3 nanoparticles obtained from thermolysis of $[Sb(S_2Ctol)_3]$ in diphenylether.

thesized by the reactions of $CuCl(PR_3)_2$, $InCl_3$ and $KSeCOAr$ in appropriate stoichiometry. These complexes on thermolysis in ethylene glycol yield tetragonal $CuInSe_2$ nanoparticles with an average size of 12 nm (from TEM)³⁹.

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Jain : Chemistry of molecular precursors for compound semiconductor nanoparticles

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